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Deliverable 22.4

ADDING CHILD CARE POLICIES IN EUROMOD

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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Introduction

In this report we document the expansion of EUROMOD with child care policies in a selection of EU countries. Child care policies have become increasingly important over the past years, especially to help families reconciling work life with their responsibilities of raising children. The rising participation of women in the labour market urged welfare states to develop and expand child care policies. Concrete child care targets for European countries were set at the Barcelona Summit of 2002. Several countries reformed or expanded their child care policies in the last decade. There are, however, still substantial differences across EU countries in terms of type and coverage of child care policies. To enhance research possibilities with respect to the distributional impact and work incentives of child care provisions, we expand EUROMOD with child care policies.

EUROMOD is a multi-country European wide tax-benefit microsimulation model. It simulates tax liabilities (direct taxes and social insurance contributions) and cash benefit entitlements for the household populations of EU Member States in a comparable way across countries on the basis of the tax-benefit rules in place and information available in the underlying datasets. Market incomes and income components which are not simulated due to lack of information (on e.g. previous employment and contribution history) are taken directly from the data. EUROMOD is a static model in the sense that the arithmetic simulation of taxes and benefits makes abstract from potential behavioral reactions of individuals. As such, EUROMOD is very suitable to assess the first order effects of tax-benefit policies in terms of income distribution, work incentives and government budgets. For further information, we refer to Sutherland (2007) and Sutherland and Figari (2013).

We have extended EUROMOD by calculating the parental fees for formal child care and other possibly related measures such as the tax treatment of these fees. In this note we describe for each country the child care policies in a selection of European welfare states and discuss the assumptions needed for implementation in EUROMOD. The selected countries are Germany, Finland, Lithuania, Netherlands, Portugal and Sweden.

1. Germany

In Germany children under 3 years old generally go to a *Krippe* or day nursery after a period of maternity leave. Early childhood education and child care services (ECEC) are provided by the municipalities. The *Länder* are primarily responsible for the education system, which includes kindergarten and pre-primary education for 3 to 6 year olds. Compulsory education starts at the age of 6 (until 15). We first discuss the German child care and pre-primary education policies (Section 1.1) and then the assumptions made to include child care subsidies and fees in EUROMOD (Section 1.2).

1.1 Child care arrangements in Germany

Child care policies have changed considerably over the last two decades in Germany. Before the reunification in 1989 child care arrangements were very different in East- and West Germany. Hence, cultural ideas on formal child care and female employment are still different in both parts of the country. From 2005 there was an increase in state-subsidised child care facilities, in 2007 the parental leave benefit was reformed and the national government, the *Länder* and the municipalities agreed on a law that introduces the legal right to day-care for all children between the age of 1 and 3 from 2013. The *Länder* have to provide sufficient places in day nurseries or day-care centers in order to guarantee a place for every child.

Work-family life policies in Germany consist of in-kind and cash benefits. The in-kind benefits include public funding for child care services and pre-primary education, while the cash benefits include parental allowances and a tax deduction for child care fees.

Maternity leave (Mutterschutz) in Germany is 14 weeks, 6 weeks before the birth and 8 weeks after the birth of a child. The contributory maternity leave benefit is paid as 100% of the average wage, which is based on the amount of a 13-week wages average or of the last 3 months before pregnancy. The *parental leave* offers both parents to stay at home and care for the child at home. The duration of parental leave can be up to 3 years, but the parental benefit is paid for 12 months at 67% of the parent's average wage (during 12 months preceding childbirth). The parental leave benefit is a contributory benefit, for parents without prior income there is a minimum payment of 300 euros per month for up to 24 months.

A third cash benefit related to child care is the *tax deduction* for children in child care. Parents are entitled to a reduction of 2/3 of the expenses for child care, capped at 4,000 euros per year. Expenses for child care include child care fees for day-care and kindergarten, fees for a nanny, a babysitter, help with homework (*Hausaufgabenbetreuung*) and benefits for caregivers (travel costs, entrance fees, accommodation and meals, etc.) (steuern.de).

Because of the recent reforms in family policy, child care attendance rates for under 3 year olds increased between 2006 and 2015 from 7 to 28% in West Germany and from 37 to 52% in East Germany. Table 1.1 shows the attendance rates for 0-2 year old and 3 to 5 year olds in the different regions. Attendance rates are much higher in preschool in all regions. For most regions attendance rates in preschool are more than 90%.

Table 1.1 Children in day-care: attendance rates ¹ of children under 3 years in day-care for children ² (1 March 2015) by Länder

Region (<i>Land</i>)	Children aged	
	0 to 2 years	3 to 5 years
Baden-Württemberg	27.8	95.5
Bayern	27.5	93.5
Berlin	45.9	95.9
Brandenburg	56.8	97.2
Bremen	27.1	91.0
Hamburg	43.3	92.5
Hessen	29.7	93.6
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	56.0	96.3
Niedersachsen	28.3	94.8
Nordrhein-Westfalen	25.9	94.5
Rheinland-Pfalz	30.6	97.3
Saarland	28.3	96.7
Sachsen	50.6	96.8
Sachsen-Anhalt	57.9	96.0
Schleswig-Holstein	31.4	93.2
Thüringen	52.4	97.2
Germany	32.9	94.9
Former territory of the Federal Republic	28.2	94.5
New Länder including Berlin	51.9	96.6

¹ Percentage share of children in day-care in all children of that age group.

² Children in day-care centres and children in publicly supported day-care provided by childminders who do not also attend a day-care centre for children or a full-time school.

Source Statistisches Bundesamt

In 2015 33% of all children younger than 6 years are in formal child care. National statistics show big differences for East-Germany and West Germany. 28% of all children under 3 years was registered in a day nursery or day-care center in West Germany (excluding Berlin) and 52% in East-Germany (including Berlin). Table 1.2 shows the number of children in day-care centers and with a childminder for 3 different age groups.

Table 1.2 Number of children in different types of day-care (1 March)

	2013	2014
Under 3 years	596,289	660,750
In day-care centers	503,926	561,569
In day-care by childminders*	92,363	99,181
3 to under 6 years	1,940,184	1,946,672
In day-care centers	1,928,461	1,934,116
In day-care by childminders*	11,723	12,556
6 to under 14 years	796,265	804,431
In day-care centers	780,778	789,441
In day-care by childminders*	15,487	14,990

* Excluding children in day-care by childminders who also attend a day-care centre for children or a full-time school.

Source Statistisches Bundesamt

Table 1.3 shows the increase of the ECEC coverage rate in Germany over the last decade. Despite increased child care places demand exceeds the supply of child care services for under 3 year old children. In contrast, pre-primary education or kindergarten is almost universal.

Table 1.3 ECEC services in Germany: participation rates, 2003-2013

	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
0-3 year	10.4	-	-	13.6	15.5	17.8	20.4	23.1	25.4	27.6	29.3
3-5 year	81.5	80.3	82.1	89.4	91.2	92.7	93.4	93.9	94.2	94.6	-

Data missing for 2004, 2005 for children in formal child care & data for 2013 not available for pre-primary education.

Source OECD family database, 2016

Child care participation rates are very low for under 1 year old children in Germany. Table 1.4 shows attendance rates per age group for under 3 year old children in the different regions.

Table 1.4 Share of children in child care under 3 years old, 1 March 2015

Land	% of children in child care between ...		
	0-1 year	1-2 year	2-3 year
Baden-Württemberg	2.6	28.1	53.4
Bayern	2.5	29.6	51.2
Berlin	2.9	56.4	81.7
Brandenburg	4.8	75.5	89.7
Bremen	1.6	29.8	52.1
Hamburg	3.1	52.5	78.6
Hessen	3.0	32.5	54.3
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	5.0	74.6	87.9
Niedersachsen	1.9	30.1	53.7
Nordrhein-Westfalen	1.7	22.6	54.0
Rheinland-Pfalz	1.7	20.3	70.8
Saarland	3.7	31.6	50.4
Sachsen	3.3	65.0	84.3
Sachsen-Anhalt	7.7	76.7	89.3
Schleswig-Holstein	2.7	35.4	55.8
Thüringen	3.1	63.3	91.2
Deutschland	2.6	35.8	61.3
Westdeutschland	2.3	28.3	55.1
Ostdeutschland	4.1	66.4	86.3

Source Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder, 2015

The cost of day-care services or nurseries in Germany depend on the region, income of the parents, number of children in the child care arrangement and the time spend in child care. Some sources indicate differences from 0 to 3,000 euro per year (Nienhaus and Hennig, 2012; Kita-Vergleich.com, 2015). Below we show a detailed description of the calculation of parental fees in Cologne.

Table 1.5 Formula for calculation of child care fees for children according to age and hours per week, city of Cologne, 2015

Age of child	Under 2 years old			2-3 year old			3+ year old		
	25	35	45	25	35	45	25	35	45
Number of hours per week in child care									
Yearly income									
Below 12,271	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
>12,271; <= 24,542	55.08	61.20	68.00	55.08	61.20	68.00	17.60	19.56	21.53
>24,542; <=36,813	120.02	133.36	148.18	120.02	133.36	148.18	31.52	35.03	42.00
>36,813;<=49,084	190.73	211.92	235.47	181.65	201.83	224.26	70.73	78.59	123.67
>49,084; <=61,355	268.64	298.49	331.65	244.22	271.35	301.50	112.85	125.39	193.94
>61,355; <=78,000	331.51	368.35	409.29	276.26	306.96	341.07	148.46	164.96	256.36
>78,000; <=100,000	430.96	478.86	532.06	331.51	368.35	409.28	178.15	197.95	307.63
Over 100,000	517.15	574.63	638.48	397.81	442.02	491.14	213.78	237.54	369.16

Source Stadt Köln, 2015

Table 1.6 Formula for calculation of child care fees for children in Offene Ganztagschule, 2015

Yearly income	Fee
Below 12,271	0.00
>12,271; <= 24,542	26.00
>24,542; <=36,813	60.00
>36,813; <=49,084	80.00
>49,084; <=61,355	100.00
>61,355; <=78,000	150.00
>78,000; <=100,000	180.00
Over 100,000	180.00

Source Stadt Köln, 2015

The cost of a child in child care is paid by the parent, the city and the region (*Bundesland*). Subsidies differ across regions. Table 1.7 shows the average subsidy for ECEC (under compulsory schooling age) in Germany.

Table 1.7 In kind benefits for public ECEC services (At current prices in national currency, in millions)

	1980	1985	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2012	2013
ECEC	1,945.8	2,300.8	3,351.0	7,188.8	6,984.2	8,559.9	11,772.8	14,446.6	16,252.4

Source OECD Social Expenditure Database

More detailed information on the expenditure per region for the most recent years is described in Table 1.8.

Table 1.8 Expenditure for child day-care centres, by Länder and rates of change, 2013-2014

Land	2013	2014	Change	
	Total		Absolute	%
	EUR 1,000			
Baden-Württemberg	2,977,860	3,144,796	166,936	5.6
Bayern	3,524,170	3,678,374	154,204	4.4
Berlin	1,221,092	1,361,913	140,821	11.5
Brandenburg	792,204	839,996	47,792	6.0
Bremen	174,797	190,901	16,104	9.2
Hamburg	558,672	580,387	21,715	3.9
Hessen	1,913,821	2,094,928	181,107	9.5
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	377,176	397,828	20,652	5.5
Niedersachsen	1,746,888	1,874,082	127,194	7.3
Nordrhein-Westfalen	4,306,463	4,600,011	293,548	6.8
Rheinland-Pfalz	1,185,813	1,274,862	89,049	7.5
Saarland	264,005	275,916	11,911	4.5
Sachsen	1,354,625	1,428,359	73,734	5.4
Sachsen-Anhalt	641,795	729,317	87,522	13.6
Schleswig-Holstein	615,420	650,916	35,496	5.8
Thüringen	604,798	610,175	5,377	0.9
Germany¹	22,270,131	23,741,065	1,470,934	6.6
Former territory of the Federal Republic excluding Berlin	17,278,442	18,373,478	1,095,036	6.3
New Länder excluding Berlin	3,770,597	4,005,674	235,077	6.2

¹ Including expenditure by the supreme federal authorities.

Source Statistisches Bundesamt

Table 1.9 Total expenditure, 2013

Total yearly expenditures	22,270,131,000
Number of children in child care services	3,332,738
Cost per child (2013)	6,682

Expenditures for all child care services so also e.g. out-of-school care.

Source Statistisches Bundesamt and own calculations

Table 1.10 Comparison of share of children in child care according to EU-SILC 2012 and administrative sources

	Day-care (r1040 in EU-SILC 2012) (in %)	Preschool (r1010 in EU-SILC 2012) (in %)	Child care in Germany (Statistische Ämter, 2012) (in %)	Professional childminder (r1050) (in %)	Family care/childminder (in %)
< 3 year	36	1	28	6	-
3-5 year	87	6		1	-

Source Own calculations based on EU-SILC 2012; Statistische Ämter

1.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD includes the simulation of maternity leave benefits and parental leave benefits. We have added the calculation of parental child care fees and the related tax deduction.

The following assumptions are made to impute child care cost in EUROMOD. Several of these assumptions are due to the fact that geographical information is lacking in the German input data for EUROMOD (EU-SILC 2012), as we do not know where the household lives (municipality nor region/Land).

- We simulate parental fees following the legislation in Cologne. Cologne is situated in the most populous region (*Land*) in Germany (Nordrhein-Westfalen). Cologne is its largest city. We do not include the rules for the capital Berlin since differences in the cost of child care are very different for parents with children under 3 years old living in Berlin or another municipality in Germany. All child care services will be for free by 1.08.2018. Until then there will be transition measures. Berlin is also characterised by a shortage of child care places. Coverage rates in Cologne are under the German average and a bit below the average in West Germany. There is a gap in coverage rates between East- and West Germany, but due to limitations of the data we cannot include region specific child care schemes. Child care attendance is taken from EU-SILC so differences between East- and West Germany are included.
- We use EU-SILC variables r1040 and r1010 to simulate the child care fees based on the number of hours in child care. We assume these variables describe the time spend in formal (subsidised) child care. The percentage is an overestimation compared to the national percentage of the *Statistische Bundesamt*. (r1040 includes most children in day-care, only 7 cases with r1010>0 for under 3 year olds. This group (r1010>0) does not change the percentage for under 3 year olds in day-care. For 3 to 5 year olds this increases the percentage to a percentage comparable with administrative information from the *Statistische Bundesamt*.
- Childminders (r1050) are treated as a separate group and are not included in the simulation of child care fees in EUROMOD
- R1030 is out-of-school or additional care so we do not include it in EUROMOD for the simulation of parental fees.
- We use Table 1.5 for the simulation of the parental fee in EUROMOD.
- For the simulation of the net subsidy for child care we use the average German subsidy and no regional differentiation.
- Based on the gross subsidy for child care (6,682 euros) and the simulated child care fee, we calculate the net subsidy for child care.

On the basis of these assumptions the rules for calculating child care policies have been modelled in EUROMOD.

2. Finland

This section provides an overview of ECEC in Finland for children under the schooling age. We describe the system and policies in place in 2015 using the most recent data available. The next section provides background information and following section discusses options for extending the modelling of child care benefits, subsidies and fees in EUROMOD.

2.1 Child care arrangements in Finland

All children in Finland are entitled to a place in public child care after the period of parental leave. This right to child care is determined by law since 1996. Child care is provided by the municipalities. The local authorities can choose to offer child care services themselves or the services can be organised by other providers and supervised by the local authorities. Parents can also choose to enroll their child in private day-care institutions. The table below shows the different types of child care for children under the age of 6.

Children start child care after a period of parental leave. *Maternity leave (äitiysraha)* lasts about 4 months or 105 working days. The maternity allowance for employees is calculated on the basis of taxed earnings of the previous tax year. The amount of the allowance is usually 70% of earnings. For the first 56 working days an increased maternity allowance is paid (maximum 90% of earnings). The *parental allowance* is also 70% of earnings in the previous tax year. An increased amount (about 75% of earnings) is paid for the first 30 working days. Both mother and father are entitled to parental leave, but not at the same time. The parental leave benefit (*vanhempainraha*) is paid for 158 weekdays to the parent who stays at home and takes care of the child. *Paternity leave (isyyseraha)* is 54 days or 9 weeks. Of this 18 days can be used at the same time as the mother stays at home, while the other 36 days should be used at a different time (when the mother is not on leave). Parents with an income under a certain threshold or who are not employed receive the (flat rate) minimum allowance of 24.02 euro per working day (2015).

Table 2.1 Child care types in Finland

	Subsidised services	Non or partly subsidised services	Other
Family care	(Municipal) Family day-care (<i>perhepäivähoito</i>) (at the home of the care provider)	Private childminder	Looking after the child at home (by one of the parents)
Collective facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipal group family day-care (<i>ryhmäperhepäivähoito</i>) (2-3 childminders look after the children, max. 4 children per care provider) - Day-care center (<i>päiväkoti</i>) (3-4 staff members, children are divided in groups of 12-21 children) 	Private day-care center	

Source Infopankki.fi; EUROMOD country report 2012-2015

If the leave allowance is exhausted parents can choose to stay at home and care for their child/children. The *child home care allowance* can be taken in two parts. The minimum length is 1 month and there should be at least one child between 0 and 3 years old. The allowance is usually used

immediately after the leave allowance and it can be used until the youngest child reaches the age of 3 or until the child goes to a subsidised child care service. The child home care allowance is integrated in the system of outsourced child care. Parents can choose the child care arrangement they prefer: they can care for the child at home, put the child in municipal day-care or in a private day-care arrangement (day-care center or childminder).

The child home care allowance consists of a basic allowance and a supplement. The basic allowance is a lump sum, the supplement is means tested. It depends on the monthly income of the family and on family size.

Table 2.2 Monthly amount of child home care allowance, 2012-2015

Child home care allowance		2012	2013	2014	2015
Basic allowance		327.46	336.67	341.06	342.53
Full supplement		175.24	180.17	182.52	183.31
Amount for each additional child under 3 years		98.04	100.79	102.11	102.55
Amount for each child from 3-7 years		63.00	64.77	65.61	65.89
Income limit & reduction rate for full supplement depending on family size					
Family size	Reduction rate (in %)	2012	2013	2014	2015
2	11.5	1,160	1,160	1,160	1,160
3	9.4	1,430	1,430	1,430	1,430
4	7.9	1,700	1,700	1,700	1,700

Source EUROMOD country report Finland

Table 2.3 shows the coverage rate for child care under 3 years old and between 3 and 5 years old. From 0 to 6 year children are in child care. At the age of 6 children are enrolled in a year of pre-primary education. Participation in pre-primary education is compulsory since August 2015, however, most 6 year olds were already enrolled in pre-primary education before it became compulsory. Compulsory education starts at the age of 7.

Table 2.3 Child care coverage rates in percentage, 2002-2013

	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
0-2 year olds	22	21	22	23	24	25	28	27	28	28	28	28
3-5 year olds	67	68	68	69	-	72	73	73	73	74	74	-

Source OECD Family database, 2016

Table 2.4 shows the number of children enrolled in child day-care services for different age groups. The percentages from the Nordic Social Statistic Committee are very similar to the OECD database.

Table 2.4 Day-care coverage rates in percentage by age group, 2002-2015

	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1-2 years	24.6	24.2	24.7	25.2	26.2	27.4	28.3	26.6	27.2	28.2	27.5	27.3	27.5	28.0
3-5 years	67.4	68.0	68.0	68.5	70.2	71.8	73.2	72.5	73.9	74.7	74.2	74.0	73.6	74.5
6 years	67.9	67.6	67.0	66.8	66.6	68.7	69.4	69.4	68.5	68.5	72.1	70.8	71.9	73.2
Total	44.4	44.4	43.8	44.0	44.7	46	47.1	46.3	46.8	47.4	47.5	47.3	47.5	48.5

Day-care includes care of all children at the different ages, whether full-time or part-time during daytime hours (6 am to 6 pm) in all institutions where attendance is checked by a public authority.

Source: Nososko, 2016

At the age of 6, children go to pre-primary education (*esiopetus*). Pre-primary education is free of charge. It is organised by the local authorities and it can take place in a day-care center, a family day-care center or a school. Compulsory education starts at the age of 7 (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2016).

The fees in municipal child care facilities are income based and depend on the size of the family and the requested hours of child care. The maximum day-care fee is 283 euros per month for the youngest and 215 euros¹ for the second youngest child in day-care. For the following children the fee is 20% of the fee charged for the youngest child. Table 2.5 shows the percentage that is charged depending on the hours in day-care.

Table 2.5 Share of full time fee for municipal day-care centres in percentage, 2015

	Day-care centers	Preschool education and day-care*
Over 7 hours per day	100	65
5 to 7 hours per day	80	40
Up to 5 hours per day	60	20

Fees for August 2014 until 31 July 2016.

* According to the Basic Education Act, preschool education is free, but day-care for children in pre-primary education is chargeable.

Source City of Helsinki, 2016; city of Espoo, 2016 (for preschool & day-care: different calculation)

The parental fee for child care also depends on the family size and the family income. The fee percentages and minimum and maximum gross income limits are described in Table 2.6 The fee is calculated by subtracting the minimum income limit (according to family size) from average gross monthly income; the fee percentage is applied on this amount to calculate the fee for full day-care of the youngest child. There is an upper bound for the fees, defined by the maximum threshold. For low-income families (i.e. those below the minimum threshold) day-care is free of charge.

¹ 255 euros in the city of Espoo.

Table 2.6 Income limits for fees for municipal day-care centres, 2015

Family size	Thresholds of gross income €/month		Fee percentage
	Minimum	Maximum	
2	1,355	3,816	11.5
3	1,671	4,682	9.4
4	1,983	5,566	7.9
5	2,116	5,699	7.9
6	2,248	5,831	7.9

* Fees for August 2014 until 31 July 2016.

Source City of Helsinki, 2016; city of Espoo, 2016

Example for the calculation of the parental fee for day-care centers: for a family with 4 persons and an average gross family income of 2,000 euros.

€2,000 - €1,983 (= minimum gross income limit, Table 1.5) = €17

€17*7.9% (= fee percentage, Table 1.5) = €1,343

The parental fee is 1.34 per month for full time day-care.

In private day-care the parental fee is determined by the service provider, but parents can receive a care allowance to cover these expenses (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2016). The private day-care compensation (*yksityisen hoidon tuki*) is paid directly to the private care provider/ child care service. The private care allowance includes a basic allowance and a supplement. The basic care allowance is 173.74 euros per month and the supplement is maximum 146.11 euros per month per child. In Table 2.7 the different income limits and reduction rates are shown. In some municipalities a family can receive a municipal supplement, when entitled to the private care allowance. The fee in private day-care cannot be more than 30 euros larger than the fee in municipal day-care. Parents can apply for the private day-care allowance from Kela (The Social Insurance Institution of Finland). The private day-care compensation (*yksityisen hoidon tuki*) is paid directly to the private service or to the private carer. It is paid after the period of the parental allowance has expired and until the start of primary school. The compensation is means tested and paid as a flat care allowance.

Table 2.7 Income limits for private care allowance supplement, 2015

Family size	Income limit €/month	Reduction (%)	No care supplement €/month
2	1,160.04	11.5	2,435.09
3	1,430.05	9.4	2,989.95
4 or more	1,700.06	7.9	3,556.14

Source Kela, 2016

Table 2.8 and 2.9 show the total expenditure to families and children in Finland over recent years. There has been an increase in the expenditures over the last decade. Both expenditures on cash benefits and on services increased. Table 2.9 shows how the expenditures were distributed over different types of care and institutions in 2011.

Table 2.8 Social expenditure on cash benefits and services for family and children, million (€), 2003-2014

	Cash benefits	Services	Total
2003	2,393	1,888	4,281
2004	2,498	1,997	4,495
2005	2,568	2,137	4,705
2006	2,607	2,240	4,848
2007	2,687	2,414	5,101
2008	2,753	2,661	5,414
2009	2,812	2,792	5,687
2010	2,957	2,888	5,845
2011	2,987	3,108	6,095
2012	3,061	3,327	6,388
2013	-	-	6,529
2014	-	-	6,573

Source Nososko, 2016; Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, 2016

Table 2.9 Expenditure on and financing of cash benefits and services to families and children, 2011

Services, million (€)	
Day-care Institutions and family day-care	2,075
Residential institutions (child and youth welfare)	619
Home help to families	22
Other	392
Services, total	3,108
Total expenditure, million	6,095

Source Nososko, 2013

Table 2.10 shows the cost of child care per child for 2011. More recent information on the cost per child is limited.

Table 2.10 Expenditure on child care, 2011

	Nososko (in €)	OECD (in US dollars)
Day-care Institutions and family day-care (million)	2,075,000,000	
Children enrolled in day-care institutions and publicly financed day-care (total)	227,000	
Cost per child (€)	9,141	12,092*

* All ECEC expenditure types.

Source Nososko, 2016 and own calculations; OECD Educational database, 2016

The compulsory year of pre-primary education can be in a day-care center or in a primary school. Government expenditures are shown in Table 2.11.

Table 2.11 Expenditure on pre-primary education (6 year olds) and primary education, in million (€)

Expenditure on	Year								Change 2013-2014 (%)
	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	
Pre-primary education	-	94	269	312	323	342	347	352	1.6
Comprehensive school education	2,379	2,734	3,413	4,120	4,231	4,363	4,492	4,538	1.0

Free of charge pre-primary education for 6-year-old children (preschool education) in day-care centres and comprehensive schools started in August 2000. Prior to August 2000 expenditure on pre-primary education in comprehensive schools is included in expenditure on comprehensive school education.

Source Statistics Finland

Table 2.12 Comparison of share of children in child care according to EU-SILC 2012 and OECD

0-2 year			3-5 year	
Day-care services (r1040 in EU-SILC)	Childminder (r1050 in EU-SILC)	Formal child care (OECD)	Day-care services (r1040,r1050 in EU-SILC)	Formal child care (OECD)
28%	3%	28%	72%	74%

Source OECD, EU-SILC 2012

2.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD does not include the simulation of maternity leave and parental leave benefits. Parental benefits are included in the microdata, it requires further research to simulate maternity or parental leave benefits in EUROMOD.

We have added the calculation of parental child care fees and the imputation of the in-kind benefits. To simulate child care fees with EUROMOD, we use the variables on child care from the EU-SILC 2012. Table 2.12 compares child care coverage rates in EU-SILC 2012 and the OECD Family database. In the simulation of child care fees, we only use EU-SILC variables that refer to formal day-care.

To impute the value of public preschool in Finland in EUROMOD, we take the following approach:

- We assume all ECEC services in Finland are subsidised. Either by the private day-care allowance or as a municipal child-care center.
- To simulate the child care fees we use the income dependent scheme of one city and simulate this for the entire country (see Table 2.5 and 2.6). Fees are regulated at the local level, but we cannot account for regional differences.
- Net subsidy is calculated using the national average gross subsidy (9,141 euros).
- We use r1040 and r1050 to simulate child care fees for under 3 year olds and 3 to 5 year olds in public or private subsidised child care services.
- The variable r1010 in Finland refers to the compulsory year in pre-primary education at the age of 6. This year of pre-primary education is free of charge, so we do not simulate a parental fee for this group (r1010>0).

3. Lithuania

This section provides an overview of ECEC in Lithuania for children under compulsory schooling. We refer to the system and policies in place in 2015, also indicating recent developments. The focus is on the form and extent of public subsidies. Section 3.1 provides background information and Section 3.2 discusses options for extending the modelling of child care benefits, subsidies and fees in EUROMOD.

3.1 Child care arrangements in Lithuania

Children under the age of 6 or 7 are cared for at home or in a child care arrangement. Under 3 year olds can go to a nursery or day-care centre, children from 3 to 5 go to a kindergarten and those aged 6 years go to preschool as a preparation for primary education. Primary education is compulsory from the age of 7. Nurseries and preschools or kindergartens can be public or private and are organised at the local level. The Lithuanian system is summarised in Table 3.1. In 2015 16% of the institutions were private (115 private institutions of a total of 721) (Statistics Lithuania, 2016).

Table 3.1 Child care system in Lithuania

	Publicly funded	Privately funded
<3	Nurseries or kindergartens	Nurseries or kindergartens
3-5	Kindergartens	Kindergartens
6	Preschool institutions or kindergartens (in kindergartens or primary schools, pre-primary preparatory groups)	Preschool institutions or kindergartens

There are different types of cash benefits for parents to care for their children at home. The maternity leave benefits (*motinystės pašalpa*), maternity/paternity leave benefit (*motinystės/tėvystės pašalpa*) and the paternity leave benefits (*tėvystės pašalpa*) are contributory benefits for parents with a newborn child. All 3 benefits are taxable and are paid from the *Law on Sickness and Maternity Social Insurance*. The maternity benefit is paid for 126 calendar days, with a replacement rate of 100% with floor/ceiling and covers the period before and after childbirth. Table 3.2 shows the replacement rate of the maternity/paternity benefit and the minimum and maximum amounts. Since the 1st of January 2012 beneficiaries can choose to stay at home for 1 or 2 years. If it is claimed for one year the benefit is 100% of the insured person's income (subject to ceilings, see Table 3.2). The paternity leave benefit can be claimed by the father during the first month after childbirth with a replacement rate of 100% with floor/ceiling.

Table 3.2 Amount for maternity and paternity benefit if claimed for two years, 2011-2016

		2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Maternity/paternity benefit (% of insured incomes)	First year	90%	70%	70%	70%	70%	70%
	Second year	75%	40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
Maximum per month for newly awarded benefits		4*CYI	3.2*CYI	3.2*CYI	3.2*CYI	3.2*CYI	3.2*CYI
Minimum per month		1/3 of CYI					

CYI is the Current Year's insured Income (einamųjų metų draudžiamosios pajamos), a state approved income threshold.

Source EUROMOD country report, Lithuania, 2011-2014

The Current year's insured income (CYI) is a state approved income threshold mainly used for purpose of state social insurance benefit calculations. The insured income is defined by *the Law on State Social Insurance Pensions*.

Table 3.3 Current year's insured income: monthly amounts for 2011-2016

	2011(LTU)	2012(LTU)	2013(LTU)	2014(LTU)	2015 (€)	2016 (€)
CYI	1,170	1,488	1,488	1,488	431	431

Source Eurostat, 2016

If eligibility conditions are not fulfilled for maternity leave benefits, a mother is entitled to the non-contributory *pregnancy grant*. The pregnancy benefit is paid 70 days before the term of childbirth and is 2 times the Basic Social Allowance (BSA). The Basic Social Allowance is a social indicator approved by the Government. It is mainly used to define and calculate social protection benefits and other statutory values (Ivaškaitė-Tamošiūnė et al., 2015). Its value was 38 euros in 2015. All families receive a *birth grant* for each born child. Its amount is at 11 times the BSA per eligible child.

After a period of parental home care, children can go to a *nurseries*, *kindergartens* or *preschool* (depending on their age). Preschools, nurseries and kindergartens are organised at the local level. The number of children in total in child care institutions and the number of child care institutions has increased over the past years (see Table 3.4).

Table 3.4 Number of child care institutions and number of children in care institutions, 2002-2015

	Number of child care institutions at the end of year units	Number of children in child care institutions at the end of the year persons	Number of places in child care institutions at the end of the year units	Number of children under 3 years old in nurseries
2002	686	90,850	85,114	-
2003	672	89,469	84,544	-
2004	655	88,423	82,843	-
2005	656	90,021	86,102	-
2006	652	90,552	87,220	-
2007	649	93,044	88,886	-
2008	654	95,136	92,134	-
2009	642	93,660	91,683	14,282
2010	626	94,737	92,244	15,927
2011	647	97,929	94,764	16,917
2012	660	104,530	107,986	19,018
2013	675	110,125	113,443	19,339
2014	690	113,657	118,309	20,038
2015	721	115,574	121,613	21,176

Source Statistics Lithuania: Ikimokyklinio ugdymo įstaigų skaičius | vnt.; Ikimokyklinio ugdymo auklėtinių skaičius | asmenys; Vietų skaičius ikimokyklinio ugdymo įstaigose | vnt., <http://www.stat.gov.lt>; Statistics Lithuania: Ikimokyklinio ugdymo auklėtinių skaičius | asmenys. <http://www.stat.gov.lt>

Table 3.5 and 3.6 show the coverage rate of children in child care. Table 3.5 is based on the Eurostat database and shows much lower attendance rates than the administrative data in Table 3.6 from Statistics Lithuania.

Table 3.5 Formal child care for under 3 year olds - % over the population of each age group

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
< 30 hours	2	0	2	1	1	2	1	3	:	6
30 hours ≤	9	4	18	8	10	12	8	5	10	17

Source Eurostat (EU-SILC)

Table 3.6 Children in nurseries, kindergartens or preschool, % of total by age and degree of urbanisation

	Rural and Urban			Urban			Rural		
	1-2 years	3-6 years	1-6 years	1-2 years	3-6 years	1-6 years	1-2 years	3-6 years	1-6 years
2000	13.7	53.1	41.1	19.9	74.4	58.0	3.2	15.6	11.8
2001	14.9	55.9	42.4	21.0	75.5	59.3	3.8	17.8	13.3
2002	16.8	60.9	47.4	24.4	87.8	63.3	3.6	26.2	19.2
2003	18.2	62.4	49.3	27.0	87.6	67.0	3.9	26.5	19.5
2004	19.9	66.1	51.5	29.6	86.5	71.1	3.9	28.9	28.7
2005	22.2	70.7	55.6	32.1	85.2	76.0	5.0	26.9	20.0
2006	26.5	72.7	57.3	35.1	83.7	77.9	6.0	28.3	21.3
2007	28.1	76.1	59.8	36.7	83.3	81.0	7.2	28.8	22.0
2008	25.4	79.2	61.0	34.9	84.1	80.8	6.7	34.0	25.2
2009	24.0	78.7	59.7	32.8	84.3	78.7	5.9	32.6	23.9
2010	22.6	79.3	60.2	34.1	82.8	76.6	7.5	35.6	26.0
2011	27.4	80.2	61.5	35.4	82.4	77.3	8.4	35.6	26.5
2012	31.4	82.0	64.4	40.3	81.4	80.1	9.7	38.3	28.8
2013	31.9	84.8	66.7	40.7	92.2	81.3	10.4	42.8	31.8
2014	33.1	86.1	68.3	42.1	97.4	82.9	11.7	44.5	33.4
2015	35.0	87.0	69.6	45.0	98.2	83.8	12.3	47.6	35.4

Source Statistics Lithuania: Vaikai, dalyvaujantys ikimokykliniame ir priešmokykliniame ugdyme
<http://www.stat.gov.lt>

The expenditures per child for the child care services are shown in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7 Expenditure per child per year in nurseries or kindergartens (€)

		Statistics Lithuania	Eurostat
Public sector	2012	-	1,262.9*
	2013	1,900	1,101.7*
	2014	2,000	-
	2015	2,200	-
Non-public sector	2012	-	-
	2013	400	-
	2014	400	-
	2015	500	-

* Expenditure per child in early childhood education, expenditure for pre-primary education is a 1,508.8 for the public institutions.

Source Statistics Lithuania: Vienam ikimokyklinio ugdymo įstaigoje ar bendrojo ugdymo mokykloje besimokančiam asmeniui teko lėšų. <http://www.stat.gov.lt>; Eurostat

Preschool fees are set by municipal councils. 80 to 100% of the fees go to meal expenditures. Lone parents, large families and families with more than one child in preschool have a discount for the meals. The municipal councils can set fees taking into account certain characteristics, e.g. the income status of parents and the child's health (OECD, 2016c).

Table 3.8 Comparison of share of children in child care in percentage, according to EU-SILC 2012 and administrative sources

	Preschool (r1010)	Professional childminder (r1050)	Formal child care arrangements (Eurostat)	Nurseries, kindergartens or preschool (Statistics Lithuania)
0-2 year	18	2*	8	31
3-6 year	76	1*	72	82

* Only 5 cases under compulsory schooling age; there are less than 10 cases in r1030, r1040 and r1050 for under 7 year old children. The child care coverage rates are very different in urban or rural regions in Lithuania (Table 3.6). Using the cross sectional weight for child care (r1070) does not or to a very small extent influence the results.

Source Own calculations based on EU-SILC 2012; OECD, Eurostat

3.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD includes the simulation of maternity and parental allowances. We have added the calculation of parental child care fees.

We use the child care variables in EU-SILC (r1030, r1040, r1050, r1010) to determine the time spent in child care. Table 3.8 shows the coverage rates based EU-SILC and the coverage rates from the OECD.

To include child care fees in EUROMOD, we make some assumptions. We will use the rules for the calculation of child care fees of one municipal institution to simulate the parental child care cost.

- We simulate parental fees following the legislation in one city: Siauliai. We cannot differentiate between regions or municipalities. We simulate the fees for children under 3 year old in nurseries and for children in kindergarten from 3 to compulsory schooling age (7 years).
- Fees in Lithuania consist of 3 parts: a fee for food, a fee for educational environment and a fee for additional services. We take into account the different parts on a monthly basis.
- An important limitation in Lithuania is the very small number of cases in child care in the EU-SILC.
- For the simulation of the net subsidy for child care we use the average Lithuanian subsidy and no regional differentiation (see Table 3.7, expenditure from Statistics Lithuania). Because the limited number of cases in child care in Estonia, and the low coverage rate compared to administrative data on child care, we assume all child care is subsidised.
- We only use r1010 for the simulation of child care fees. Table 3.8 shows this might be an overestimation, but we cannot further distinguish other types of care.
- No values in r1030 for children under compulsory age, except for one case (6 year old). This could indicate that this variable includes out-of-school-care. Same goes for r1040: no cases under compulsory schooling age. r1050 (childminder) includes only 5 cases for children under compulsory schooling age.
- For the gross subsidy we use the cost per child from Statistics Lithuania (Table 3.7).
- Due to strong assumptions to include child care fees in Lithuania, we would not use the simulation of child care fees and subsidies for distributional analysis.

4. Netherlands

ECEC in the Netherlands have been decentralised to the municipalities over the last two decades. The responsibility of ECEC is spread over different Ministries. In Section 4.1 we describe the parental and non-parental child care arrangements in the Netherlands. How to include child care fees in EUROMOD and calculate subsidies is discussed in Section 4.2.

4.1 Child care arrangements in the Netherlands

Different ministries of the national government are responsible for the organisation of ECEC. The Ministry of Education, Culture and Science is responsible for mainstream and special education, preschool education and educational disadvantage policy. Child protection and fostering, and for crime prevention and combating is a responsibility of the Ministry of Justice. Policies for the combination of work and care tasks falls under the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment and the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Kingdom Relations is responsible for integration policies for ethnic minorities.

The first care arrangements after childbirth is the cash benefit for *maternity leave* for the mother and the delivery leave for the father. The maternity allowance is 16 weeks and equals 100% of earnings (until a maximum). 4 to 6 weeks should be used before the day of delivery, the other 10 to 12 weeks can be used after the birth of the child. The partner of the mother is entitled to *delivery leave*. A paid delivery leave of 2 days is agreed in the Framework Act Labour & Care, the length should be in consultation with the employer. Additionally both parents are entitled to *unpaid parental leave* for a part of the working time, until the child reaches the age of 8 years. An employee should work at least 20 hours. Parental leave is used predominantly by mothers.

From 0 to 6 years old there are different non-parental child care services for children. *Preschool playgrounds* are for 2 and 3 year old children, *child day-care* for all children aged 0 to 3 and out-of-school-child care for 4-12 year old children. Most children start primary school at the age of 4 (until 12) but compulsory education starts from the age of 5. Children with special needs or health problems can use specific services: (educational) development programmes and parent support programmes and specialised youth care schools for special education and child protection agencies (OECD, 2000; Rijksoverheid, 2016). The total number of children in child care increased until 2011. After 2011 there was a decrease. Table 4.1 also shows most children are in day-care services.

Table 4.1 Number of children per type of child care, x1000, 2007-2015

	Total	Day-care	Out-of-school care	Family care
2007	572.8	291.7	206.5	122.9
2008	708.5	330.0	267.6	189.5
2009	782.1	352.7	313.9	203.6
2010	804.0	383.1	349.1	152.5
2011	835.5	395.9	372.3	147.8
2012	821.5	387.5	369.7	140.6
2013	774.8	357.8	353.5	136.8
2014*	755.0	344.2	346.2	136.0
2015*	767.0	344.0	355.9	140.9

* Provisional number.

Source CSB

Most children in the Netherlands are not in full time child care. Table 4.2 shows much higher coverage rates for children that are less than 30 hours in child care.

Table 4.2 Formal child care by age group and duration - % over the population of each age group, 2005-2014

Age	Duration	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
< 3 years	< 30 hours	36	41	39	41	43	44	46	39	40	39
	30 hours ≤	4	4	4	6	6	6	6	7	6	6
3 years - c.a.	< 30 hours	82	82	80	77	75	76	76	75	71	74
	30 hours ≤	7	7	11	12	12	15	13	14	15	14

c.a. = compulsory school age.

Source Eurostat

The average parental contribution for child day-care is 6.83 euros/hour in 2015. The parental contribution in the total share of child care costs was on average 27% in 2011, ranging from 11% to 45% (CBS, 2013). There is an income dependent scheme for the calculation of child care fees, with higher rates for higher incomes. The maximum price for day-care for 0-4 year olds is 3.84 euros/hour in 2015 and 6.89 euros/hour in 2016. For out-of-school care, 4-12 year old children, the maximum hourly cost 6.42 euros in 2016 (6.38 euros in 2015). For family care (0-12 year) the maximum hourly cost is 5.52 euros in 2016 (5.48 euros in 2015). Depending on household income, the child care allowance is calculated, which is a benefit paid by the tax authorities to enable parents to pay for child care. To be eligible for the child care allowance the child has to go to a registered child care service and the parents have to work/study or look for work. The benefit consists of an income dependent part, paid for by government budget and a part dependent on the actual child care costs, paid for by the employer. With a household income of 107,155 euros, parents receive a child allowance (*kinderopvangtoeslag*) of 23.8% (2016). If parents have an income of 21,806 euros they receive 93% of the costs as a child care allowance (*kinderopvangtoeslag*). A higher income means less child care allowance. The minimum is 23.8% for the first child and 64% for the second child.

There is no formula to calculate the child care allowance. The tax administration uses a table that is updated every year (see Table a1.2 in the Appendix). Additionally to the child care allowance, there is an *income dependent combination rebate*. To receive this rebate one of the parent has to earn an income from labour, his/her child has to be under 12 years old and there is no partner or a partner with a

lower income from labour than his/her partner. For people under the pension age (*AOW-leeftijd*) the deduction is calculated according to Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Calculation income dependent combination deduction for the child care allowance, 2015

Labour income above (in €)	Labour income under (in €)	Income dependent combination deduction
-	4,857	No deduction, except if you are entitled to a deduction for self-employed, than: € 1,033.
4,857	3,832	€ 1,033 + 4% x (Labour income - € 4,857)
32,832	-	€ 2,152

Source rijksverreid.nl

The tables below show the expenditures for the child care allowance and child care services in general over the last decade. The share of the government has been decreasing, while the share of the employer and the parents has been an increasing part in the total child care costs. Table 4.4 shows detailed information of the budgets spend on child care by different actors. The cost per child in calculated in Table 4.5 based on the total budget and the number of children in child care.

Table 4.4 Budget child care allowance and children using the child care allowance, 2005-2015

		2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Budget child care allowance												
Expenditures child care allowance	€1mln	673	921	2,058	2,825	3,035	3,313	3,178	2,707	2,322	2,175	2,148
- Government contribution	€1mln	673	921	1,589	2,166	2,351	2,636	2,469	1,688	1,251	1,122	1,056
- Compulsory employer contribution	€1mln	0	0	469	659	684	677	709	1,019	1,071	1,053	1,092
Revenues child care allowance	€1mln	43	71	48	67	119	401	408	401	415	450	416
Net expenditures = expenditures – revenues allowance	€1mln	630	850	2,010	2,758	2,916	2,912	2,770	2,306	1,906	1,725	1,732
Net government expenditures = government contribution - revenues	€1mln	630	850	1,541	2,099	2,232	2,235	2,061	1,287	835	672	640
Share in financing child care												
Parents	%	37	30	18	18	21	22	27	33	40	38	38
Employers	%	21	22	26	23	21	23	21	35	34	38	40
Government	%	42	48	56	59	58	55	52	32	26	24	22
Number of children using child care allowance (x1000)												
Cost per child (for child care allowance) (€)		2,164	2,693	4,235	4,708	4,361	4,634	4,300	3,818	3,703	3,463	3,310

Source kinderopvang.nl, CSB, own calculations

Table 4.5 Government subsidy for child care, 2015

Total expenditure (million)	2,121
number of children in formal child care (x1,000)	755
Cost per child	2,809

Source CBS, rijksbegroting, own calculation

Table 4.6 Comparison of share of children in child care according to EU-SILC 2012 and CBS

Age of children	Total (%)		Children in day-care (%)	
	CBS	EU-SILC (r1040+r1050)	CBS	EU-SILC (r1040)
0	23	49	18	39
1	46	72	35	65
2	53	82	42	76
3	56	65	46	38
4	54	45	20	0

Source CBS, own calculations based on EU-SILC 2012

4.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD does not include the simulation of maternity leave or parental leave benefits. It requires further research to simulate maternity or parental benefits in EUROMOD.

We have added the calculation of parental child care fees and the related tax deduction. The following assumptions are made to impute child care cost in EUROMOD.

- We simulate child care fees, using the child care allowance and the income dependent combination rebate for children under the age of 4. For 4 years old we assume children go to primary school. We do not simulate additional out-of-school-care for children aged 4 or older.
- Almost all children aged 4 have a value > 0 for pre-primary education (r1010). So from the age of 4 we assume full time attendance in (pre)primary education.
- R1030 includes out-of-school hours child care, the variable is '0' for all under 3 year olds, so we do not include this variable in the calculation of the cost of child care.
- R1040 and r1050 are overestimations
- We simulate the same fee for day-care and family care.
- We use the number of hours reported in the variables in EU-SILC.
- We use both the subsidies for the child care allowances and other government subsidies to calculate the net subsidy per child. Because most children in under 4 year day-care are entitled to the allowance, we assume all children in day-care receive the allowance. (Less children in out-of-school-hours care are entitled to the allowance. This group is not included in the simulations.)

On the basis of these assumptions the rules for calculating child care policies have been modelled in EUROMOD.

5. Portugal

ECEC in Portugal have been reformed over the last years. In the first section we describe the current system of parental (/maternity) leave and non-parental child care. In Section 5.2 we discuss the inclusion of child care subsidies and fees in EUROMOD.

5.1 Child care arrangements in Portugal

After childbirth, there is a period of parental home care. The parental leave is 150 calendar days in total (if the parents share the leave, if only one parent takes leave this is only 120 days). The first period is 6 weeks (42 calendar days) and is obligatory for the mother. The remaining days can be divided by both parents with the possibility for 30 extra days if parents share the leave period. The parental cash benefit is paid to employees as part of the compulsory social insurance scheme. The *parental benefit* is related to previous earnings. 120 days are paid at 100% or 150 days at 80% of earnings. There is a minimum payment of 11.18 euros per day if the level of earnings is very low. The benefits are paid by the social insurance scheme. After the parental leave period each parent is entitled to 3 months of *additional parental leave*. This leave is an individual entitlement, with a benefit that amounts to 25% of average earnings over the last 3 months (before maternity leave). Unpaid parental leave can be up to 2 years.

Two different systems of ECEC can be distinguished, one for children under the age of 3 (regulated by the Ministry of Solidarity, Employment and Social Security) and one for children between 3 years old and compulsory schooling age (regulated by the Ministry of Education). Over the last decade there has been an increase of child care participation rates in Portugal due to the investment in preschool education. Participation in ECEC has been increased to 41% in 2014 (see Table 5.1). Child care services for under 3 years old children are child day-care centers and day-carers (partly informal). The investment in preschool education has been an important feature of Portuguese social policy. The access to child care has been increased, mainly with regard to full-time services for children under 3 years old.

Table 5.1 Share of children in child care, 2005-2014

Age	Duration	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
< 3 years	< 30 hours	4	1	2	2	2	5	1	:	2	4
	30 hours ≤	26	32	25	31	34	32	34	34	36	41
3-5 years	< 30 hours	12	9	14	9	8	11	7	5	5	6
	30 hours ≤	26	32	25	31	34	32	34	34	36	41

Source Eurostat

Child care rates are much higher in pre-primary education for 3-5 year old. Table 5.2 shows the gross enrolment rates in pre-primary education per school year. In recent years around 90% of the children is enrolled in pre-primary education.

Table 5.2 Gross enrolment rates in pre-primary education (%) by Geographic localisation (NUTS - 2002); Annual 2005-2014

	2005/ 2006	2006/ 2007	2007/ 2008	2008/ 2009	2009/ 2010	2010/ 2011	2011/ 2012	2012/ 2013	2013/ 2014	2014/ 2015	2013 2014
Portugal	78.6	78.5	79.8	83.4	85	87.4	90.9	90.6	89.8	90.9	89.8
Contínente	78.1	78	79.5	83.2	84.7	87.2	90.9	90.4	89.6	90.8	89.6
Região Autónoma dos Açores	85.4	86.6	83.5	86	89.6	90.1	90.2	92.1	93.5	92.9	93.5
Região Autónoma da Madeira	89.3	87.7	87.2	87.9	90	91.2	94.7	94	93.6	95.1	93.6

Source Annual - Gabinete de Estatística e Planeamento da Educação, Statistics Portugal

Child care fees in Portugal are determined as a percentage of household income, that increases with income. The maximum fee cannot be higher than the real average cost (including administration expenses) per user of the service. If more than one child in a family goes to the same child care service, the fee is reduced. 30% of child care costs for formal child care arrangements can be deducted from taxes. The limit for this deduction is 160% of the National Minimum Wage and this maximum increases for families with more than 3 children.

Most child care services in Portugal are public services and services organised by NGO's. The monthly subsidy for semi-public subsidised services in 2012 was 242.79 euros per child. Child carers (nannies/ childminders can also benefit from these arrangements (OECD, 2016c). The first type is fully subsidised by the government. Most children in pre-primary education are in public services. Children under 3 year olds are partly in the first type (fully subsidised child care), partly in semi-subsidised child care (flat rate state support) and partly in private child care. The distribution of all children in child care by type of child care is described in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3 Distribution of total children in ISCED 0 (%) by type of institution (2012)

Public	Government-dependent private	Independent private
53.2	30.4	16.5

Source OECD Education at a glance 2014

Parents with children in semi-public services pay an income-dependent child care fee. The table below shows the calculation of child care fees for different income scales. Low-income families or a family with an income below 30% of the guaranteed monthly minimum income (RMMG) pay a fee that is 15% of their per capita income. The household income per capita is calculated according to the following formula:

$$RC = (RAF/12 - D)/n$$

RC is the income per capita, RAF is the gross household income, D stands for the fixed costs of the household and n is the number of household members.

Table 5.4 Calculation of the parental contribution in family day-care and crèches, in percentage

Income scale (% of RMMG)	Below 30%	30%-50%	50%-70%	70%-100%	100%-150%	>150%
Day-care	15.00	22.50	27.50	30.00	32.50	35.00
Out-school-care without food costs	5.00	7.00	10.00	12.50	15.00	15.00
Out-school-care including food costs	12.50	15.00	17.50	20.00	22.50	22.50

RMMG = guaranteed monthly minimum income; Out-of-school-child care (CATL) is focused on children from 6 to 15 years old.

Source Instituto da Segurança Social, 2015

Table 5.5 and 5.6 show the total expenditures and the cost per child in ECEC.

Table 5.5 Total expenditures on ECEC (At current prices in national currency, in millions)

	1980	1985	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2012	2013
ECEC	0.3	0.7	2.2	4.8	354.5	593.0	696.0	634.2	624.5

Source OECD Social Expenditure Database

Table 5.6 Annual expenditure on educational institutions per pupil based on FTE, by education level and programme orientation [educ_uoe_fini04]

	2012	2013
Early childhood education	3,388.4	3,896.8
Early childhood educational development	:	:
Pre-primary education	3,388.4	3,896.8

* See Appendix; Table a1.3 for annual expenditure in USD using PPPs from the OECD Education at a glance 2016.

Source Eurostat

5.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD does not include the simulation of maternity leave and parental leave benefits. Parental benefits are included in the microdata, it requires further research to simulate maternity or parental benefits in EUROMOD.

We have added the calculation of parental child care fees. The following assumptions are made to impute child care cost in EUROMOD.

- We use EU-SILC child care variables for information on the time spend in a child care arrangement. We include r1040 and r1010 to simulate child day-care and preschool. Variable r1050 (care by childminders) is not included. For under 3 year olds we only use r1040.
- We randomly select which children under the age of 3 age in public child care (free of charge, fully subsidised by the government), in semi-public child care (subsidised by a flat rate) and in private child care. We use the proportions from Table 5.3.
- Public child care or pre-primary education is fully subsidised and free of charge. For semi-public child care we simulate one set of rules for the income dependent fees, we do not differentiate between type of child care and region (see Table 5.4).
- We have limited information on the fees for private child care, so we simulate an average monthly cost for private child care, we do not include regional variation.
- We assume all public day-care centers and nurseries receive subsidies. For public child care and pre-primary we use the subsidies from Table 5.6. We use the most recent cost per child (2013), we do not index this cost. For semi-public child care we assume a flat rate subsidy.
- We also include the tax reduction for parents who pay a fee for child care in EUROMOD, following the policy rules.

On the basis of these assumptions the rules for calculating child care policies have been modelled in EUROMOD.

6. Sweden

This section provides an overview ECEC in Sweden for children under the schooling age. We describe the situation in 2015. The next section provides background information and Section 6.1 discusses how EUROMOD has been extended.

6.1 Child care arrangements in Sweden

In Sweden child care has traditionally been publicly provided. Nowadays the private facilities occupy a minor place in the child care landscape. These private facilities are also subsidised. From the age of one year children are predominantly present in preschool. Until this age most children are cared for at home. Per child parents are entitled to 480 days of *paid parental leave* (*Föräldrapenning*, cash benefit). Each parent can take half of these days, 60 days are reserved for the father and 60 days are reserved for the mother. 390 days are paid at 80% of earnings, the remaining 90 days at a flat rate. In 2013 men took almost 25% of all parental benefit days. Table 6.1 shows the minimum and maximum amounts. To increase the incentive for parents to share the parental leave and participate in working life, there is an equality bonus. The *equality bonus* is SEK 50 per day per parent. Most days of the equality bonus are paid before a child's third birthday. Conditions to receive the bonus are joint custody when the parents receive parental benefit, it is only paid after the 60 days reserved for each parent have been taken and when the parent who has taken the fewer number of days receives the parental benefit. Other parental benefits are the temporary parental benefit for care of children, the temporary parental benefit in connection with the death of a child, the temporary parental benefit for contact days and the temporary parental benefit in connection with birth or adoption.

Table 6.1 The parental benefit

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Paid parental leave as % of earning, maximum amount per day in SEK	910	901	910	935	946	-
Paid parental leave as % of earning, minimum amount per day in SEK	180	180	180	180	180	180
Paid parental leave, flat rate per day in SEK	180	180	180	180	180	180

Source Sweden.se , Försäkringskassan

If the work conditions make it impossible to work, a pregnant woman can apply for a *maternity allowance/ pregnancy benefit* during maximum 50 days. The benefit rules are the same as for the sickness benefit. The benefit is taxable.

Child care or kindergarten starts from the age or 1. Child care services are provided for children aged 1 to 5. The year a child turns 6, he/she can participate in a non-compulsory preschool year. Compulsory school age is 7 years (compulsory school is until 16).

Table 6.2 Child care types in Sweden

	Subsidised	Non subsidised	Other
Family care	Family day-care home (with one or more childminders) (1-12 years)	/	Informal care (friends or family) (Everyone that takes care of children, except for family, has to report.)
Collective facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preschool (1-5years) - Pedagogical care - Leisure time centers/ recreation centers - Open preschools 		

Source The Swedish Education System

Preschool/kindergarten (*Förskola*) is for children aged 1 to 5, but children start preschool at different ages. Preschool hours are from 6.30 to 18.30 every weekday, except for certain public holidays. Children can attend for varying hours. Preschool is organised by the municipalities. 3 types of child care services can be distinguished in Sweden (See Table 6.2). Preschool services, family day-care homes and open preschools. The municipalities are obliged to provide family day-care or preschool for children aged 1 or older. Preschool places are for children when their parents are working or pursuing studies or when their parents are unemployment or on parental leave. For unemployed parents or parents on parental leave a place is to be made available to each child for at least 3 hours a day or 15 hours a week. A place in preschool is to be offered within 3 or 4 months after the parents notified the municipality of their requirement. Preschool services also have to offer ‘universal preschool/ordinary preschool’. This means municipalities have to offer preschool places for all children for at least 525 hours per year or 15 hours per week free of charge for all children from the age of 3 until the age of five (NOSOSKO, 2013). In 2014 about 80% of the children from one to five years of age spend part of their weekdays in preschool education. Most children attend preschool **full time**.

The year a child turns 6, he/she is eligible to start preschool class (*Förskoleklass*). The preschool class is voluntary and free of charge. It prepares children to start compulsory school at the age of 7. Attendance is usually 3 hours a day, during the rest of the day, the pupils are in the leisure-time center or in pedagogical care. Preschool classes are organised by the municipalities.

In a family day-care home a childminder receives children into his or her home. The children are between 1 and 12 years but most are between 1 and 5 years old. Concerning the provision of places, family day-care homes also have to offer a place for a child without unreasonable delay and a place has to be made available for at least 3 hours a day or 15 hours a week.

Open preschools are for children and their parents together. Children can do educational activities while the adults have a chance for social contact. Many open preschools cooperate with other activities, such as social services or maternal and child health care. The visitors are not enrolled but decide themselves when and how often they want to attend. This type of child care will not be discussed further in this note.

The number of preschool institutions and the share of enrolled children between 2008 and 2015 are shown in Table 6.3.

Table 6.3 Number of preschool institutions and enrolled children, 2008-2015

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Municipal level								
Number of preschool institutions	7,447	7,280	7,223	7,339	7,267	7,142	7,208	7,106
Number of enrolled children	354,616	362,990	370,290	380,263	387,357	391,874	393,428	397,254
Percentage of enrolled children (%)	82	81.4	80.9	80.5	80.3	80.1	81.0	80.5
Other (family care, other type of public care, etc.)								
number of preschool institutions	2,502	2,586	2,646	2,694	2,724	2,749	2,655	2,668
Number of enrolled children	78,005	83,090	87,706	91,898	94,952	97,401	92,715	96,642
Percentage of enrolled children (%)	18.0	18.6	19.1	19.5	19.7	19.9	19.1	19.5

Source Skolverket

For children aged from 6 to 12 years (schoolchildren) after school care (*Fritidsbem*) is available in family day-care homes, leisure time centers or open leisure time centers. This form of child care is also organised by the municipalities. From 7 to 16 children are required to attend primary school. Primary school and the non-compulsory preschool year (preschool class) are free of charge and include a hot lunch.

Parents are also entitled to general child allowances for a child in Sweden, until the quarter they turn 16. We will not discuss child allowances here.

Between 2001 and 2003 Sweden carried out a reform on parental fees for child care. The maxtaxa reform entailed the introduction of a maximum parental fee and the obligation for municipalities to keep available preschool slots for certain groups. Since the reform fees ought to be related to gross income. Municipalities are allowed to charge a reasonable fee for a preschool place, but there is also a maximum fee system. This means that there is a cap on how high fees can be for a family. The maximum fee system is voluntary for municipalities. The municipalities who apply it are entitled to a government grant to compensate them for loss of income and to secure quality. Since 2003 all municipalities in Sweden apply a system with a maximum fee. The tariff system is based on the household income, the maximum monthly cost for the first child is SEK 1,287 (140 euros in 2015).

The maxtaxa reform states that parents should only have to spend one to 3% of the family's income on child care, depending on how many children they have. Table 6.4 shows the formula. The fees are a percentage of the gross monthly household income. For fee-based income the following is *not* counted: Maintenance allowance/maintenance support, Child allowance, State study support, Housing allowance, Disability allowance, Maintenance support/Financial assistance/Social allowance, Municipal care allowance, Establishment allowance, Compensation from the Swedish Migration Board.

Table 6.4 Fees for preschool and family day homes (1-2 years), 2014-2016

	Child care fee	Maximum amount (per month)		
		2014 (in SEK)	2015 (in SEK)*	2016 (in SEK)
Child 1	3% of income	1,260	1,287	1,313
Child 2	2% of income	840	858	875
Child 3	1% of income	420	429	438
Child 4	Free of charge	0	0	0

The youngest child in the family counts as 'Child 1'.

* The fees for 2015 apply from 2015-07-01.

Source <http://www.avesta.se/In-English/English/Fees-for-child-care-/>; Skolverket, 2007; Lund.se; Lulea.se

The fees for preschool and family day homes for 3 to 5 year olds differ more from municipality to municipality. The fees are always lower than the fees for 1-2 year olds (e.g. 2.1%; 1.4% and 0.7% for the first to third child in Avesta in 2014).

Table 6.5 Fees for after school and leisure time centers (differences between municipalities possible), 2014-2016

	Child care fee	Maximum amount (per month)		
		2014 (in SEK)	2015 (in SEK)	2016 (in SEK)
Child 1	3% of income	840	858	875
Child 2	2% of income	420	429	438
Child 3	1%/0.7%* of income	420	300	438
Child 4	Free of charge	0	0	0

The youngest child in the family counts as 'Child 1'.

* In the city Lund.

Source <http://www.avesta.se/In-English/English/Fees-for-child-care-/>; Skolverket, 2007; Lund.se; Lulea.se

Since the maxtaxa reform the proportion of children enrolled in preschool had increased in all municipalities. In the family day-care homes both the proportion and the number of children have decreased, but this development has been in process from before the maxtaxa reform. The parental fee in preschool or a leisure time center does not depend on the attendance time. Since the reform the attendance time at preschool and family day-care home has decreased. Also the attendance time in leisure time centers has fallen.

The availability of preschool institutions is very high, while the availability of leisure time centers varies among municipalities. In 2013 47.3% of the children under 3 years old are in formal child care in Sweden. 94% of the children aged 3 to 5 are in preschool educational programmes in 2012 (OECD, 2016). Since maternity leave is relatively long in Sweden, child care only starts for children aged 1. The majority of Swedish children attends publicly financed child care between 1 year and 5 years. A smaller group is in after-school care (7 to 12 years).

Child care is organised at the municipal level but has a national financial framework. Government expenditure on pre-primary education in Sweden in 2009 is 22,558 million SEK. The expenditures rose to 24,895 million SEK in 2011. Table 6.6 shows an overview of the total cost for preschool and child care services.

Table 6.6 Total expenditure and cost per child on ECEC

	2009	2013	2014
Total cost (thousand) (SEK)	50,641,955	62,222,631	65,095,038
Enrolled children	466,470	489,275	485,721
Cost per enrolled child (SEK)	114,400	128,100	133,500

Source Skolverket, 2016

The responsibility for the operation of services to families and children rest with the local authorities. The municipalities have to provide preschool or family day-care. The government expenditure on preschool programmes is 22,558 million SEK (see Table 6.7). The average parental copayment is 7% of the total cost per child (Skolverket, 2016).

Table 6.7 Annual government expenditures preschool, 2008-2011

	2008	2009	2010	2011
SEK, millions	21,310	22,558	23,716.1	24,895.2

Source OECD Education Database

6.2 Data and simulations

Currently, EUROMOD does not include the simulation of maternity leave benefits. It requires further research to simulate maternity or parental leave benefits in EUROMOD.

We have added the calculation of parental child care fees and the related tax deduction.

To impute the value of public preschool in Sweden in EUROMOD, we take the following approach:

- We assume all ECEC services in Sweden are subsidised. Child care and preschool variables all taken together. Also r1030 (out-of-school care) is included because for 3 year olds there are only two cases with r1030>0 and for children older than 3 this could include afternoon care if there are in (free) preschool. If children attend child care/preschool we assume they attend full time and calculate a full time fee. Fees are calculated on a monthly basis. For children from 3 to five years old we simulate that 15 hours per week are free of charge. For these children we reduce the monthly amount so they only pay part time child care. For the calculation of the fees we assume a maximum of full time day-care so additional care and the cost of this additional care is not simulated.
- For 1-2 year old children we use the information Table 6.4 to simulate parental fees.
- For 3-5 year old children we simulate 15 hours of free child care, for the additional hours in child care we use the income dependent scheme for the calculation of child care fees
- At the age of six, children can go to preschool class (non-compulsory).The preschool class is free of charge but the additional child care is not. Based on the child care variables r1030, r1040 and r1050 we calculate the fee for the additional care. This fee depends on the amount of hours in the care institution.
- Fees are regulated at the local level, but we cannot account for regional differences.

appendix 1

Table a1.1 Attendance rates ¹ of children in Germany under and above 3 years in day-care for children ², 1 March 2016 by Länder

Land	Children aged	
	0 to 2 years	3 to 5 years
Baden-Württemberg	27.7	94.7
Bayern	27.2	92.9
Berlin	45.9	94.9
Brandenburg	57.2	95.5
Bremen	27.0	87.8
Hamburg	42.9	90.0
Hessen	29.7	92.8
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	56.0	95.4
Niedersachsen	28.4	93.2
Nordrhein-Westfalen	25.7	92.3
Rheinland-Pfalz	29.9	96.6
Saarland	28.6	95.4
Sachsen	50.6	95.5
Sachsen-Anhalt	57.0	94.1
Schleswig-Holstein	30.9	92.7
Thüringen	52.2	95.6
Germany	32.7	93.6
Former territory of the Federal Republic	28.1	93.2
New Länder including Berlin	51.8	95.2

¹ Percentage share of children in day-care in all children of that age group.

² Children in day-care centres and children in publicly supported day-care provided by childminders who do not also attend a day-care centre for children or a full-time school.

Source Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder, 2015

Table a1.2 Child care allowance tables, including social contribution, percentage of costs of child care, Netherlands 2015

Household income from (in €)	Household income below (in €)	Child care allowance (in %)	Child care allowance (in %)
		First child	Second child/ following children
Below	17,918	90.7	93.3
17,919	19,111	89.1	93.3
19,112	20,303	88.1	93.3
20,304	21,496	87.4	92.9
21,497	22,690	86.7	92.9
22,691	23,882	86.0	92.9
23,883	25,076	85.0	92.9
25,077	26,265	84.2	92.9
26,266	27,549	83.4	92.7
27,550	28,831	82.6	92.2
28,832	30,114	81.5	91.9
30,115	31,397	80.9	91.6
31,398	32,681	79.9	91.6
32,682	33,964	79.0	91.4
33,965	35,278	78.2	91.0
35,279	36,594	77.3	90.8
36,595	37,909	76.5	90.6
37,910	39,224	75.6	90.0
39,225	40,541	74.5	89.8
40,542	41,857	74.0	89.5
41,858	43,172	73.0	89.5
43,173	44,487	72.3	89.2
44,488	45,925	71.2	89.0
45,926	48,743	69.4	88.5
48,744	51,562	68.5	87.7
51,563	54,382	67.1	87.1
54,383	57,202	64.5	86.6
57,203	60,020	61.8	86.3
60,021	62,840	59.1	85.5
62,841	65,659	56.3	85.0
65,660	68,478	53.5	84.4
68,479	71,299	50.9	83.6
71,300	74,117	48.2	83.1
74,118	76,938	45.5	82.6
76,939	79,757	42.6	82.3
79,758	82,574	39.9	81.5
82,575	85,393	37.3	81.1
85,394	88,269	34.5	80.5
88,270	91,157	32.0	79.7
91,158	94,044	29.6	79.2
94,045	96,930	27.0	78.8
96,931	99,818	24.4	78.4
99,819	102,705	21.7	77.6
102,706	105,593	19.0	77.0
105,594	108,480	18.0	76.5
108,481	111,366	18.0	75.9
111,367	114,254	18.0	75.5
114,255	117,141	18.0	74.7
117,142	120,028	18.0	74.1
120,029	122,915	18.0	73.0
122,916	125,801	18.0	72.6
125,802	128,689	18.0	71.8
128,690	131,578	18.0	70.7

Household income from (in €)	Household income below (in €)	Child care allowance (in %)	Child care allowance (in %)
		First child	Second child/ following children
131,579	134,464	18.0	70.1
134,465	137,351	18.0	69.1
137,352	140,238	18.0	68.5
140,239	143,126	18.0	67.7
143,127	146,013	18.0	67.0
146,014	148,900	18.0	66.2
148,901	151,786	18.0	65.1
151,787	154,673	18.0	64.5
154,674	157,561	18.0	63.7
157,562	160,448	18.0	62.9
160,449	163,335	18.0	62.1
163,336	166,223	18.0	61.4
166,224	169,110	18.0	60.6
169,111	171,997	18.0	59.8
171,998	174,884	18.0	59.2
174,885	En hoger	18.0	58.2

Source belastingdienst.nl

Table a1.3 Annual expenditure by educational institutions per student (in USD using PPPs) in Portugal, 2012-2013

	Pre-primary	All early childhood education		
		Public	Private	Total
2012	5,713	-	-	-
2013	6,604	6,684	6,511	6,604

Source OECD, Education at a glance 2016

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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